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CHILD AND THE FAMILY IN THE PRESENT CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT :

With the rapid change in the culture of our country, the traditional values seemingly changing in Indian society and especially in the family. Family is considered as the most important social agent in the child's social network because the members of the family constitute the child's first environment. Family environment lays the foundation for patterns of adjustment attitude development, and personality. For a child, family is the mirror of the world in a nutshell. It is the family that provides for physical, social and psychological needs and guides them in times of trouble. This gets deeply imbibed in the minds of the child which reflects on the personality of the child. Hence positive family relations from childhood to adolescents will influence the behavior of child and it has to be nurtured right from the young age by proper care. This paper will highlight the issues of family relations during childhood

and adolescence and also identify some tips for improving better family relations.

KEYWORDS : Family Relations, Home Environment, Tips for Better Family Relations.

INTRODUCTION

Family is the most important part of the child as the child's social network is designed and shaped by the family members. The child's first environment is the family and hence it is where the sum total of the child in terms of behavior, approach, values, character, etc. are formed. As the child starts to learn from home during this formative stage, it has a significant role in the development of relationships. Researches in various behavioral sciences over the decades confirm that different behavior patterns of people are due to what happened during the first few years of their lives. The child's family relationship is shaped at the early childhood and hence proper care and importance is to be given in bringing up the child as it will reflect on adolescence all round development.

MODERN FAMILY

The modern family is mostly nuclear family with members as father, mother, children and rarely grandparents. There has been a profound modification of the economic, social and biological nature of the family because of modernization. Technology has taken up more works at home leading the women to get employed. With both parents working the attention, love, care, warmth the child receives in the yesteryears has vanished. This results in the depletion of values, belief, and change in culture of the family and the individual at large.

GROWING WITH THE FAMILY TRANSMITS VALUES AND BELIEF'S

Family is the smallest social unit in which the child spends from childhood to adulthood. It is the place where the child accepts, shares, adjusts, learns, feels secure, thinks, etc. When healthy relationship in family prevails, the child feels secure and comfortable and remains well adjusted and feels that the society accepts him. Mutual conflicts and quarrels among the family members cause the child always tensed. He feels himself rejected by the society and in turn rejects the society. He becomes disrespectful and disloyal to society. These experiences of children with their family grow in them either a sense of acceptance or rejection which they generalize in due course. As the child grows and comes in contact with peers and adults outside the home, these early foundations laid in the home, may influence later attitudes and behavior pattern.

FAMILY RELATIONS AND PERSONALITY

Human personality develops in a social environment and in childhood the personality of an individual is susceptible to variation and modification. According to Richard L. (1959) personality is shaped in the first few years of life and parents are the chief architects in shaping the personality of the child. It can be molded similarly just as a twig is bent in a certain direction and tree grows accordingly. Children learn them early and learning persists to adulthood. Berelson Band G.A. Steiner (1964) in his view feels opinions, attitude and beliefs are inherited psychologically and sociologically from one's parents. Sociologists believe the variations in personality patterns to difference in child rearing practices of the parents. Parents influence their children in several ways, explicitly through instructions and selective reinforcements or through their own behavior. Furthermore the attitude of the child resembles closely to the value patterns of their family. So proper nurturing of the child at the very young age is the key to shaping the personality. Therefore family relations form a strong influence on

the child's personality as the child grows.

BALANCING PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIP IN THE FAMILY

Excessive neglect and excessive love and affection are not to be desired in the relationship between the child and parents as both are the origin of challenges concerning the personality. If the child is placed under excessive control, his personality is not allowed to develop and he is obsessed with a sense of inferiority and if the child is given much freedom he does not develop any respect for authority and cannot be governed. The fact of the matter is child rearing is an art and one has to balance based on instincts, sound psychology and patience. It is a continuous learning process for the parents to find the best and mutually acceptable way at all times and at all situations as there is no fixed manual of dealing with children.

FAMILY RELATIONS DURING ADOLESCENCE

Developmental theories view adolescence as a period of growth in which identity formation is addressed. A great deal of emphasis is placed on the importance of peer groups, and how they become more influential than parents at this age. Children develop identity by forming relationships with peers, and expand on their friend circle. They feel close to the peers and love spending time with them than with their family. Strong bond formation between cliques develop loyalty, support, among the members of the group. The number of friend in the group keeps on changing based on the nature of the group. At this stage it is normal for young people to begin to think for themselves and question aspects of their lives and of family relationships. These changes may mean times of anger and frustration that is leveled at the family, but in the majority of circumstances these feelings are likely to be temporary or circumstantial. Although the nature of relationships is changing, the continuity of family connections and a secure emotional base is crucial for the positive development of young people. Parents will benefit from being supported to understand the role of rebellion in young people's development. Limit has to be setup for poor or unacceptable behaviour which has to be communicated in a way which is proper and acceptable to both.

Tips for Better Family Relationship

- Accept and respect feelings of children
- No comparison with other performances
- Encouraging and supporting hobbies of children
- Encourage each other with praise rather than being critical.
- Allowing the social media relations in a healthy environment
- Friendly relationship with children's friends
- Not fixing higher goals than their abilities
- Understanding the emotional swings of the members
- Respecting individual differences
- Accept and encourage personal habits
- Use time together, such as mealtimes, to talk and share a laugh.
- Have one-on-one chats with each family member to build and strengthen individual relationships.
- Sharing of joy and sorrow
- Do fun things together as a family on a regular basis.
- Make decisions together about what to do for special events such as birthdays.
- Talk about everything (even difficult things).

- Listen with full attention to each other.
- Make it OK to talk about feelings (even the bad ones).
- Work together to solve issues and address problems effectively.
- Discipline with love, patience and understanding.
- Show appreciation, love and encouragement through words and affection.
- Respect peer relations of the child
- Occasionally visit family and friends.
- Allow weekend get together at home with their peer during adolescence.

CONCLUSION

The family especially the nuclear family is the most universal social group for children in the modern era. No culture or society has ever existed without some form of family organizations. The family is in a way biological unit having a common dwelling place for its members. Children who form the core in this setup bring joy and happiness to everyone around in the family. Positive relations between children and parents are pivotal for the growth and development of the child from childhood to adolescence, as it will prepare the child for life. So it is time to focus on the family relations between children and their parents so as to help parents and teachers to deal with children constructively as they grow.

REFERENCES:

1. Blum, R. & Rinehart, P. (1998) Reducing the Risk: Connections that Make a Difference in the Lives of Youths.
2. Duncan, S. and Brown, G. (1992). RENEW: A Program For Building Remarried Family Strengths. *Families in Society*, 73(3), 149-158.
3. Fuller, A. (2000). *Raising Real People: Creating a Resilient Family*. Melbourne: ACER
- Howe, D., Brandon, M., Hinings, D. and Schofield (1999). *Attachment Theory, Child Maltreatment and Family Support. A Practice and Assessment Model*. Palgrave: Houndmills, Basingtoke, Hampshire and New York.
4. Kagitcibasi, C. (2002). Rites of Passage to Adulthood: Adolescence in the Western World (Review of the Book *Negotiating Adolescence in Times of Social Change*). *Human Development*, 45, 136-40.
5. Laurson, B. (1995). Conflict and Social Interaction in Adolescent Relationships. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 5, 55-70.
6. Muuss, R. (1996). *Theories of Adolescence*. New York: McGraw Hill (6th ed.).
7. Daniel, B., Wassell, S. & Gilligan, R. (1999). *Child Development for Child Care and Protection Workers*. UK: Jessica Kingsley Publishers.
8. Steinberg, L. (2001). We Know Some Things: Parent-Adolescent Relationships in Retrospect and Prospect. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 11(1), 1-19.

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